

RELATING DISTRIBUTIVE JUSTICE TO ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR AMONG CIVIL SERVANTS IN KENYA

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Abstract: Countries depend on their civil service for the achievement and implementation of social, economic, and environmentally sustainable development as the machinery that design, formulate and implement policies, strategies, and programs, and discharge the routine functions of the state. This study aimed at exploring the relationship between distributive justice and organizational citizenship behavior among civil servants in Kenya. Distributive justice is critical in achieving increased employee morale, reduced turnover, and productive culture. This study was informed by increased counterproductive work behaviors among civil servants which have resulted in poor quality services to citizens. A cross-sectional research design was adopted to study three hundred and seventy-five employees who were selected through simple random sampling to respond to a structured questionnaire. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The results confirmed the existence of a positive and significant relationship between distributive justice and organizational citizenship behavior; correlation coefficient, $R = .625$, $P = .000$; coefficient of determinant, $R\text{-squared} = .391$, ANOVA results with significant $F\text{-value}$ and $T\text{-value}$ for the Beta coefficient. The study concluded that distributive justice was a critical factor in inspiring organizational citizenship behavior of civil servants in Kenya and should be by civil service management to improve performance. This result adds to the existing knowledge, and theory and confirms the dimensionality of distributive justice in an African cultural setting.

Keywords: Organizational justice, Distributive justice, organizational citizenship Behaviour, Civil Service, Kenya.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the unpredictable business environment and intense competition due to globalization, changes in technology, and political and economic environments organizations are required to reach certain standards by improving their performance to achieve competitive advantage [1]. As a means of sustaining effective performance employees are a crucial resource and the most determining factor, being the intellectual property of the firm [2]). This is because, without the support of qualified human resources, an abundance of infrastructures or physical facilities will be made meaningless; this will

directly disrupt the continuity of the business operations [3]. For many countries, the civil service is the core on which the achievement of holistic, integrated, and participatory implementation of social, economic, and environmental dimensions of sustainable development is dependent. Being the machinery that the government relies on to design, formulate and implement policies, strategies, and programs, and to discharge the routine functions of the state, it needs to be effective and efficient; civil servants need to be inspired and perform their tasks beyond the call of duty, and display positive behaviors, like organizational citizenship behavior.

Organizational citizenship behavior is a contextual performance outcome. Researchers argue that, in organizational performance, overall employee job performance is not a function of task and contextual performance alone, but also of counterproductive work behaviors [4]. Counterproductive work behaviors are viewed by an organization as contrary to its legitimate interests, violating significant norms, and threatening the existence of the very organization or its members [5]. [6], acknowledge that organizations are better off when helpful behaviors are optimized and harmful ones minimized. Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) is such a helpful behavior.

Organizational justice is one of the leading components that can influence organizational citizenship behaviors [7]. When individuals believe that the treatment they get is fair, other things being equal, they are more likely to perform OCBs [8]. Fairness, especially in the distribution of resources and outcomes in an organization is critical in achieving increased employee morale, giving them a sense of being valued, and reducing their turnover intentions. When there is fairness in distributing amounts of valued work-related outcomes, done objectively, it will inspire employees into a performance culture that can lead organizations to productivity. This notion forestalls the importance of distributive justice as a factor that makes employees exhibit positive behavior at the workplace. Distributive justice can inspire employees to change from counterproductive to positive behaviors like organizational citizenship behavior.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The review of literature is based on the variables under study as follows:

2.1. Organizational Citizenship Behaviour

[9], defines OCB as a positive attitude that consists of employees' ability to persist with enthusiasm, conform to rules and regulations, assist other employees, and openly defend the organization's objectives. The initial conceptualization of OCB was done by [10] who defined it as a discretionary, individual behavior, not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal reward system, but which in the aggregate promotes the effective functioning of the organization. [11], redefined OCB as the contributions made by employees to the maintenance and enhancement of the social and psychological context that supports task performance. This definition held that the conceptualization of OCB was the same as that of contextual performance and included behaviors such as volunteering, demonstrating effort, helping and cooperating with others, following rules and procedures, and supporting organizational objectives [12], [11]. Therefore, building OCB among employees is critical for any organization that seeks innovation, creativity, and initiative and hence sustainable competitive advantage [13].

The concept of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) was first defined by Bateman and [14] as discretionary individual behavior, not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal reward system, and which in the aggregate promotes the effective functioning of an organization. [11], later expressed OCB as an employee performance that supports the social and psychological environments in which task performance takes place. Further definitions and illustrations on OCB have noted its need in organizations. [15], acknowledge that OCB has been recognized as employee behavior that can shape the social and psychological context where core job responsibilities are accomplished and uniquely contributes to overall organizational performance. In true spirit, Organizational citizenship behaviors are positive behaviors that enable employees to perform their jobs beyond formal job descriptions [16] and can lead employees to have a good soldier syndrome; invest effort and energy in their social environment with no expectations of formal reward. OCB is a vital behavior to the survival of an organization; it maximizes the efficiency and productivity of both employee and the organization, and inherently strive for employees to extend their discretionary behaviors beyond the expected duties.

Organizational Citizenship Behaviours include traditional in-role behaviors, extra-role behaviors, and political behaviors that enhance full and responsible participation [17]. They are a range of cooperative behaviors that are positive, intended,

non-obligatory, and that go beyond the set requirements of a job. These behaviors are not directly related to the main task activities but are significant because they support the organizational, social, and psychological context that serves as the critical catalyst for tasks accomplished [18]. [19], describe OCB as optional behaviors, that are not included in job descriptions or formal behavior requirements in an organization, but are behaviors of personal choice such that their omission is not generally understood or punishable.

The reason for the development of organizational citizenship behavior was to explore employee characteristics that are cooperative and helpful and that provide a constructive contribution to the organization [20]. OCBs are necessary for the good functioning of an organization as they mean doing a better job, making an effort above and beyond formal requirements, and filling the gap between procedures and regulations. [21], concurs that they lead to exerting good behavior for the sake of the organization by informally supporting its members. OCB helps employees extend beyond the performance indicators in the formal job description and reflects employee actions that surpass the minimum role requirements. They are good behaviors and extraordinary endeavors that organizations expect from their members to achieve success [22]. OCBs occur when a worker embraces an organization's core values to such a degree that the person is inspired to go beyond job rewards and requirements and to act in ways that will improve the workplace [23]. In OCB, employees willingly contribute extra effort to the attainment of organizational outcomes, and supervisors cannot demand or force their subordinates to perform. Since the behaviors are voluntary, they contribute to superior performance by increasing co-worker productivity, helping coordinate activities within and across workgroups, reducing the need to devote scarce resources to purely maintenance functions, and strengthening the organizational ability to attract and retain the best employees.

Researchers have different views concerning the dimensionality of OCB., for example, two dimensions composed of altruism and generalized compliance [24], three dimensions made up of organizational obedience, organization commitment, and organization participation [25]; seven dimensions comprising of helping, sportsmanship, loyalty, compliance, individual initiative, civic virtue and self-development [26]. However, the most used taxonomy for OCB is the five dimension model propounded by [14] of altruism, courtesy, conscientiousness, civic virtue, and sportsmanship. Although most scholars have adopted the Organ (1988) model, this presents a lack of consensus on the concept and sometimes overlaps in its dimensionality [27], hence the need for more research as proposed here to understand the concept more from different scenarios.

To understand this concept fully, this study adopted the five model structure of OCB which has altruism, courtesy, conscientiousness, civic virtue, and sportsmanship. [28], define altruism as a helping behavior where a worker helps a fellow employee with work-related problems. Civic virtue is the participation of an employee in the governance by voluntarily participating and supporting organizational functions of both professional and social nature. Conscientiousness refers to employees carrying out their duties beyond the minimum requirements of tasks [29]. Courtesy is the behavior where an employee alerts other organizational members about changes that may affect their work. Sportsmanship refers to an employee's refrains from complaining about trial matters by willingly tolerating the inevitable inconveniences [30].

2.2. Organizational Justice

Research has proven the existence of immense interest and more attention in organizational justice because it denotes how people perceive fairness and justice in their organizations [31]. [32], argue that organizational justice is how employees evaluate organizational behavior and their resulting attitude and behavior. Based on the equity theory, organizational justice is the employees' opinion of whether the organization is treating them fairly or not [33]. In case the employees perceive that they are treated unfairly by the organization or the managers, and subject to the social exchange theory, they will feel a breach, which may lead them to pull out, lower performance, increase absenteeism, reduce job commitment, perform their jobs poorly, and ultimately leave the organization [34], [35].

Organizational justice has been conceptualized differently by different researchers, either as a three or four-dimensional model concept. [36], has noted that the widely accepted conceptualization is the three model structure that has distributive, procedural, and interactional justice. Cropanzano, Rupp, and Meghan (2016) confirm this model and refer to it as the big three dimensions, and add that, although the model continues to be widely used, and characterizes most of the work on justice, it is not the only structural approach to organizational justice. These scholars support the four-model

structure advocated by [37] that includes distributive, procedural, informational, and interpersonal justice. This is similar to [31] who points out that recent studies categorize the perception of justice into four components: the justice in procedures in establishing outcome distributions (procedural justice); the fairness of resources and rewards distribution (distributive justice); the excellence of interpersonal treatment when a certain course of actions is put into practices (interpersonal justice); and the adequacy of information exchanged explaining the reasons for such procedures being used in a certain way or how such results were established (informational justice). This study focused on one of the dimensions, distributive justice, to identify whether it had a relationship with organizational citizenship behavior among civil servants in Kenya and add to the existing literature on the study of organizational justice and OCB in an African setting where such research is still limited.

2.3. Distributive Justice

Distributive justice is therefore one of the dimensions of organizational justice. Distributive justice refers to the extent to which benefits are allocated equitably in an organization. It focuses on employees' beliefs that they receive fair amounts of valued work-related outcomes (Greenberg & Baron, 2008). It is the perception of equitable practices in output distribution made by supervisors or organizations [38]. It justifies treatment based on ethical and objective criteria among workers such that benefits are distributed similarly among similar individuals and differently to different individuals. In distributive justice, and based on the equity theory, employees measure the fairness of distribution of resources by comparing their inputs to their outcomes, and against those of co-workers for the same work category [39]. In these comparisons, when they feel unfair treatment, they may change their behavior by decreasing their input to their organization.

The foundation of distributive justice is derived from Aristotle's Nichomachean Ethics which emphasized the allocations of respect and funds or the stuff that was to be distributed amongst the employees who had a claim on the resources of the organization [31]. According to Aristotle, the distribution of resources in an organization, to which employees were entitled, had to be done based on established ethical standards and was to be done fairly. As articulated in the social exchange theory of Homans, social relationship creates expectations amongst parties, and employment as a social relationship expects that the rewards of every employee shall be based on the cost he/she bears and that the net return received should be in proportion to theirs. The reward each employee receives shall be based on his involvement or input and by no means be based on the contribution or input of any other employee. In case this happens, an employee with higher input or contribution and another low input or contribution receives equal reward or benefit in the same organization then this would amount to an injustice.

[40] acknowledges that distributive justice is fairness in awarding outcomes among employees based on equity, equality, and need while [33] argues that perceptions about distributive justice are primarily shaped by comparisons, where employees evaluate their reward and position by making a comparison with the person staying in the same stratum, within the organization or with persons having the similar position outside the organization. On the other hand [41] noted that people are not merely fascinated by physical outcomes, they also pay significant attention to whether those outcomes are justified or not justified, and commensurate with the performance in the workplace.

Much of the research on distributive justice is found in the works of [41]. Adams suggested the equity theory and supposed that it could be used to determine the fairness of the distribution of an outcome to individuals. According to equity theory, individuals look at how much they get- outcomes, relative to how much they contribute- inputs. Workers will compare the ratio of what they get to that which is given to co-workers and this ratio then helps them to decide whether the organization has been or not been fair. Employee inputs in the organization include brainpower, know-how, preparation, ability, skill, time, energy, cognitive and emotional struggle, and expected rewards are salary, holidays, supervisor support, freedom of decision, respect, admiration, position, and social identification, basic work equipment and facilities.

Accordingly, distributive justice will be felt in the appropriateness of the outcomes and their allocations, such that those employees who deserve may get it while those who don't will miss out [42]). It is concerned with equity, equality, and need [43]. In equity, employees are rewarded based on their contributions such that those who contribute more are rewarded appropriately. In inequality employees of one level are provided with roughly the same level of compensation

such that the contributions made to the organization by individual employees should be proportional to their income. In-need benefits are provided based on employees' requirements [42].

This measure of fairness is perceived in the distribution and allocation of pay structures, benefits such as promotions, and office assignments. Outcomes such as pay/salary, benefits, satisfying supervision, job status, and a variety of the formally and informally sanctioned pre-requisites are comparable to the individual attributes like effort, education intelligence, experience skills, seniority, age, sex, ethnic background, and social status [44]. If an employee feels that their payment is less than expected, it affects their emotions and attitudes, and ultimately their performance drops. Hence distributive justice is a critical factor for some types of organizations for their functioning and in need of sustaining competitive advantage.

2.4. Relationship between Distributive Justice and OCB

OCBs can be termed as employees' inputs to their organization hence the perceived distributive justice certainly affects these behaviors. The employees' belief, confidence, and trust in the fair distribution of outcomes can motivate them to engage in spontaneous behavior. Individuals with a high degree of distributive justice perception will dedicate themselves to making their organizations develop, engage in self-development, and concentrate more on the work they do [45]. When people perceive that they enjoy fairness in reward distribution for their extra effort, they may engage with more work. Likewise, when employees feel their treatment is according to ethical and objective criteria, it encourages them to perform more, particularly displaying OCB.

Therefore, it makes sense that distributive justice has a positive relationship with OCB. The review of literature associating justice practices with organizational citizenship behavior is present. [34] investigated how justice practices were related to citizenship behavior in organizations in two management firms in the United States. The outcome of the study proved that the relationship was positive and significant. [46] investigated fairness and organizational citizenship behavior. The study wanted to find out the connections between these variables. Using literature review, they found ample evidence to support the importance of fairness, in both distributive and procedural terms, in accounting for OCB. A large study conducted by [43] reviewing 183 empirical studies on organizational justice found an overwhelming relationship among all justice constructs and many outcomes found in organizations that included satisfaction with one's job, commitment to the organization, evaluation of authority, OCB, a tendency to withdrawal, and overall performance. In the Malaysian higher education system, Ahmad (2006) discovered that distributive and procedural justice were related positively to the citizenship behavior of teachers. [47], showed that if workers had negative feelings about resource distribution and the procedures used to allocate the resources, they tended to lower their job performance, loyalty, and low citizenship behavior.

[48], collected data from 177 educational experts working in education departments in Tehran (Iran) to identify whether organizational justice could cause organizational citizenship behavior and whether perceived organization support mediated the relationship. The study found that organizational justice practices, especially distributive justice indirectly influenced organizational citizenship behavior. [49], surveyed Punjab (Pakistan) and collected data from 300 teachers and 60 heads of secondary schools. The study found that organizational behavior and distributive justice were significantly correlated. [50] an Iranian study of school teachers found a significant relationship between organizational justice dimensions and organizational citizenship behavior.

Therefore organizational citizenship behavior is one of the most widely linked outcomes of Organizational Justice practices [42]. The link between employees and the organization is on an exchange relationship of social or economic resources. OCB, being a construct identified as a measure of contextual performance, is dependent on the social exchange theory. OCB, driven by social exchange, is a give-and-take behavior of materials and non-material goods and is based on the norm of reciprocity such that one who receives a benefit from another is obliged to repay the favor [51]. Therefore OCB can be supported by the high-quality relationship between those who work for the organization, the organization, and subordinates and supervisors. As a reciprocity behavior, the norm of reciprocity makes workers and employers relook at their differences and similarities to value each other and consider the contract between them to be like a trade-off of effort and loyalty. Since employee-organizational relationships are reciprocity and fairness in the distribution of resources is one reciprocity tendency of the organization to employees.

2.5. Research Model

The study was based on the following model

Fig 1: the Conceptual Framework

This model shows the relationship between the dependent and the independent variable. This model captures the objective of the study “to investigate the influence of distributive justice on organizational citizenship behavior of civil servants in Kenya”.

2.6. Hypothesis

From the study of literature and the stated model the following hypothesis was derived:

H₀: there is no relationship between distributive justice and organizational citizenship behavior of civil servants in Kenya.

H₁: There is a relationship between distributive justice and organizational citizenship behavior of civil servants in Kenya

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey design based on the quantitative research approach. The design was selected because data were collected at one point in time for it was to be used to describe trends, determine individual opinions about policy issues, and help identify important beliefs and attitudes [52] of civil servants. The cross-sectional design allows a study to use a questionnaire in collecting data and statistically analyzing the data to describe trends [53].

3.2 Population, Sample, and Sampling Techniques

The population of this study was civil servants in Kenya. There are 240 000 civil servants. The study targeted eleven thousand six hundred and seventy-one (11671) civil servants who work in ministries and departments in Kakamega, Kisumu, Nandi, and Vihiga. Three hundred and seventy-five (375) employees were selected from this population to constitute the sample. A multistage sampling technique was used to provide an equal opportunity for each employee to participate in the study [44]. In the first stage, four counties were purposively selected based on the rule of the thumb constituting approximately 10% of all counties in Kenya. In the second stage, employees were categorized into their ministries and departments using stratified sampling techniques. Thereafter, a simple random sampling technique was used to select the 375 employees based on a self-weighted technique from each ministry. Data were collected from ten ministries that have a presence in the selected regions. This is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Sample Size Design

Ministry	Kakamega	Vihiga	Nandi	Kisumu	Total	Proportion %	Sample Size
1 Interior and Coordination	2035	805	1836	2092	6768	59	221
2 Labour and Social Protection	60	20	75	98	253	2.2	8
3 Information & communication	145	85	100	280	610	5.2	20

4	Public Service, Youth & Gender	50	20	40	50	160	1.4	5
5	Environment and Forestry	80	30	70	70	250	2.2	8
6	Lands	70	20	80	120	290	2.4	9
7	Transport and infrastructure	230	80	160	310	780	6.7	25
8	MOEST	300	200	300	300	1100	9.5	36
9	National Treasury	120	20	80	180	500	4.3	16
10	Energy	250	100	220	250	820	7.1	27
	Total	3580	1380	2961	3750	11671	100	375

3.3 Data Collection Instruments

A questionnaire was the instrument used to collect the data. The questionnaire covered all the indicators of variables used. The questionnaire was structured because it had statements presented with the same wording and in the same order to all respondents who were to reply to the same set of statements using the same five-point Likert scale. The questionnaire was found appropriate for the study because it helped cope with the constraints of limited time and budget and could limit the respondents to given aspects of the variables in which the study had an interest. The content of the questionnaire was adapted from various studies and hence it was subjected to exploratory factor analysis through principal component analysis to assess its validity [54]. This is shown in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2: Factor Analysis for Distributive Justice

	Initial Extraction	Final extraction	Decision	% of Var. Explained
My work schedule is fair	.664	Complex	Removed	67.635
My pay is fair	.696	.832	Retained	
My workload is fair	.530	.665	Retained	
All rewards are fairly given to all	.707	.748	Retained	
Responsibility is fairly awarded	.702	.784	Retained	
All rewards are awarded competitively	.625	Complex	Removed	
My work schedule allows me to do personal work	.911	Complex	Removed	

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

From exploratory factor analysis, out of the seven statements for distributive justice, three statements were removed leaving it with four items that explained a 67.635% of the total variance in the variable based on eigenvalues greater than 1.

Table 3: Factor Analysis for OCB

	Initial extraction	Final extraction	Decision	% of Var. Explained
I always obey rules even when not supervised.	.805	.898	Retained	69.484
I voluntarily attend non-mandatory meetings important for the organization's image.	.796	.885	Retained	
I always consider the impact of my actions on coworkers.	.699	.815	Retained	
I take fewer days off work and mostly give advance notice if unable to attend.	.687	.821	Retained	
I share out useful information and make innovative suggestions to improve their organization.	.795	.858	Retained	
I spend a great deal of time in personal telephone conversations during work hours	.939	Complex	Removed	
I willingly help others who have been absent or have heavy workloads.	.587	.730	Retained	
I am punctual at work and mostly remain on duty	.675	.810	Retained	
It takes initiative to help new employees even when it's not my duty	.723	.840	Retained	

From exploratory factor analysis, out of the nine statements for organizational citizenship behavior, one statement was removed leaving it with eight items that explained a 69% of the total variance in the variable based on eigenvalues greater than 1. Before conducting principal component analysis, the statement had been checked for their Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett's test of sphericity. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: KMO and Bartlett's Test for Distributive Justice and OCB

	KMO	Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
Organizational Citizenship Behaviour	.911	202.524	28	.000
Distributive Justice	.749	28.976	6	.000

Table 4 shows that the variable had a KMO measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett's test of sphericity within the recommended level. Based on this analysis, the statements not removed were tested for reliability. The reliability for distributive had a Cronbach's alpha value of .805 while that of organizational citizenship behavior had .779. The measurement scale for organizational citizenship behavior was adapted from [14] while that of distributive justice came from [55].

Table 5: Table for Reliability

Variable	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Distributive Justice	4	.805
Organizational Citizenship Behavior	8	.779

3.4 Data Collection

The study collected both primary and secondary data. However, for analysis mainly primary data was used. Before collecting data necessary permission was sought and granted. The questionnaire was self-administered and was distributed to participants who were then allowed time to fill it in. The fully filled-in questionnaires were collected for analysis. Four hundred (400) questionnaires were distributed to help reduce the incidences of drop out. However, after collection 290 questionnaires were found to be well filled and suitable for use in the analysis.

3.5 Data Analysis

Before the Collected data were analyzed, all questionnaires were reviewed to determine whether they were all filled up to the requirement. Incompletely filled questionnaires were checked; their level of completeness was determined and those which were poorly completed according to the set criteria were rejected and removed from the list of all collected questionnaires. Those which could be edited were revised. Those questions/statements which were found suitable were then cleaned and fed into the computer through the SPSS version 21 software for analysis. The following model was set for determination during analysis.

$$Y_{OCB} = \beta_0 + B_1X_1 + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots\text{Bivariate regression Model}$$

Where: Y_{ocb} = the dependent variable, Organizational Citizenship Behaviour; β_0 = Constant term; B_1 = coefficient of relationship; X_1 = the independent variable, Distributive Justice; ε = error term

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Response Rate

The sample size was 375. From this sample, 375 were targeted and 290 responded by filling out the questionnaires completely. This resulted in a response rate of 77%. The response was satisfactory according to [56].

4.2 Demographic Characteristics

Demographic information was set on gender, education level, number of years they had worked, their employing ministry, county, and job category. Based on gender 54% were men while 46% were female. Concerning academic qualifications 5% had o-level education, 23% had certificate qualifications, 38% had diplomas, 26% had bachelor's degrees while 8% had a postgraduate qualification. In region or county, 32% worked in Kisumu, 26% worked in Nandi, 31% worked in Kakamega, and 11% worked in Vihiga. According to departments, 14% worked in the public service ministry/department, 7% ministry of Energy, transport and infrastructure, 5%, 5% for interior, 2% for treasury, 14% for social service, 1% for environment and Forestry, 11% for education science and technology, 11% for ICT, while 2% for lands ministry. On job experience, 13% had worked for less than 2 years, 24% had worked for between 2-5 years, 27% had worked for between

5-10 years, and 37% had worked for over 10 years. In the job category, management staff was 11% while the non-management staff category was 89%.

4.3 Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive analysis is mainly aimed to enable a study meaningfully describe the distribution of scores or measurements using indices or statistics [57]. The descriptive statistics used included frequencies, percentages, the mean, and standard deviation. The results are shown in Tables 6 and 7 for the two variables.

Table 6: Descriptive Results for Distributive Justice

Statement	SD	D	N	A	SA	M	SD
	%	%	%	%	%		
My pay is fair	16	28	23	22	11	2.82	1.251
My workload is fair	14	27	23	25	11	2.92	1.263
all rewards are fairly given out	13	31	21	24	10	2.86	1.224
Responsibility is fairly awarded	13	31	19	21	16	2.95	1.296
Average	15	28	21	24	12	2.87	1.271

From Table 6, the mean measures for each statement are all below 3.0 with an average mean of 2.87. This shows that respondents were not in agreement with the statements on distributive justice. This could indicate that the dimensions of pay, workload, rewards, and responsibilities in the civil service in Kenya are not fairly distributed. The standard deviation for each dimension is greater than 1. This shows that the respondents had very little agreement on the statements on distributive justice; the standard deviations indicate a large variability of the opinion. This may mean that in truth inequality exists in staff perceptions of distributive justice; there is a presence of inequity. Based on this assessment, it is valid to indicate that these perceptions may be the main cause of negative feelings in job performance and hence the difficulty in employees' ability to improve their performance. Therefore, inequality perceptions in staff promotions, high-grade delegations, and other awarding systems in the public sector may be the cause of anger and dissatisfaction. This could lead to distractive tendencies among employees and which may have reduced their ability to contribute more to the civil service performance hence the poor services.

Table 7: Descriptive Results for Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Statement	SD	D	N	A	SA	M	SD
	%	%	%	%	%		
I always obey rules even when not being supervised	19	35	25	11	5	2.49	1.107
I voluntary attend important but not mandatory organizational meetings	21	39	20	16	5	2.50	1.076
I am always mindful of the impact of my behavior on others	26	36	17	15	6	2.32	1.021
I always take fewer days off duty and give notice when absent	23	36	25	13	4	2.43	1.061
I always share useful information which benefits the organization	25	36	25	11	3	2.57	1.054
I willingly help others who have been absent or have heavy workloads	9	22	27	31	12	3.16	1.154
I am punctual at work and mostly remain on duty	12	25	21	31	13	3.09	1.230
It takes initiative to help new employees even when it's not my duty	6	25	20	35	14	3.27	1.156
Average	23	36	22	12	5	2.39	1.13

Table 7 shows that the mean average for the statements is 2.39. This indicates that the respondents did not agree with the statements and therefore do not display citizenship behavior. An observation of the standard deviation shows an average of 1.13. This indicates that the respondent had varied opinions; there were a lot of differences. This may show that

inequity and inequality exist and some may be displaying citizenship behavior, for being treated well, while some do not display for being treated not so well. This could be the reason a majority of the respondents do not display citizenship behaviors and therefore cannot engage in any extra-role behaviors that can benefit the civil service and therefore improve its performance. Studies have shown that disparities exist in the pay structure, promotions, and responsibilities in the civil service in Kenya. The situation is very worse when comparing the earnings of the top management and low cadre workers. This could explain the high levels of withdrawal behavior, and the reason why the majority of civil servants just go to their workplaces to perform their normal duties and cannot engage in any work which can benefit or help improve the public service's ability to provide quality services to service seekers.

4.4 Regression Analysis

The study set two hypotheses:

H₀: there is no significant relationship between distributive justice and organizational citizenship behavior of civil servants in Kenya.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between distributive justice and organizational citizenship behavior of civil servants in Kenya

A regression analysis to determine this relationship was performed to find out whether to adopt the null or the alternative hypothesis. The regression results in table 8 provide the basis for the choice of the hypothesis.

Table 8: Regression Results for Distributive Justice

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.625 ^a	.391	.388	.51706		
a. Predictors: (Constant), Distributive Justice						
ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	49.332	1	49.332	184.519	.000 ^b
	Residual	76.998	288	.267		
	Total	126.331	289			
a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Citizenship Behaviour						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Distributive Justice						
Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.166	.129		16.820	.000
	Distributive Justice	.473	.035	.625	13.584	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Citizenship Behaviour						

From Table 8 the model summary results show the coefficient of determination for the relationship, R- squared = .391. This reveals that distributive justice accounts for 39.1% of the total variance in OCB of civil servants in Kenya and the rest, 60.9% is contributed by other variables not studied here. This R square result indicates the existence of goodness of fit for the regression line between distributive justice and OCBs. It shows that the relationship is linear with a moderate to high coefficient of relationship $R=0.625$.

The ANOVA results have $F(1, 288) = 184.519$, $P < 0.05$ (sig. = 0.000). This indicates that the overall model was significant because the observed F - value (184.519) is far large than the critical F - value at the given degree of freedom (3.87). Therefore it is true that distributive justice significantly influences the organizational citizenship behavior of civil servants in Kenya and the two variables are related.

The coefficients for the relationship, Beta value =0.473, P=.000. They imply that a unit change in distributive justice in the civil service will lead to a positive change in OCBs of civil servants in Kenya by a rate of 0.473 units or 47.3% with the constant of the relationship $B^0 = 2.166$. This result provides the following as the model of the relationship and the predictive model between distributive justice and OCB in civil service in Kenya.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + e \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Where

Y_{OCB} = Organizational Citizenship Behaviour

β_0 = constant (coefficient of intercept)

X_1 = Distributive Justice

e = error

Hence, the final model was:

$$Y_{OCB} = 2.166 + 0.473X_1 + e \dots\dots\dots \text{Model 1}$$

The results found in this study indicate that there is a positive and significant relationship between distributive justice and organizational citizenship behavior among civil servants in Kenya. The study, therefore, rejects the null hypothesis that *'there is no significant relationship between distributive justice and organizational citizenship behavior of civil servants in Kenya* and adopts the alternate hypothesis, *'There is a significant relationship between distributive justice and organizational citizenship behavior of civil servants in Kenya'*.

These results are similar to those obtained by [51] in a study 'organizational Justice leading to Citizenship Behavior: A Study of University Education Faculties in Punjab (Pakistan)'. [42], a study 'organizational Justice and Organizational Citizenship Behavior among Store Executives in Bangalore,' also found that distributive justice positively affected organizational citizenship behavior

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, organizational citizenship behavior is influenced by several factors, among them organizational justice. The results indicate that some employees feel treated unfairly while others feel treated fairly. This may mean that some employees have negative attitudes towards the civil service. These feelings may lead to decreased effectiveness and efficiency of the civil service in service delivery [38]). [58], argues that based on the equity theory, distributive justice is promoted where outcomes are consistent with implicit norms for allocation of equity or equality while distributive injustices such as inequitable pay raises or unfair distributions of workload constitute harms or losses to employees.

This study concludes that distributive justice and organizational citizenship behavior are related among civil servants in Kenya. Equality and equitable distribution of organizational outcomes such as pay, rewards, responsibilities, and workload are key indicators of distributive justice and they should be done based on ethical principles and the laid down procedures. Indeed, all workers cannot be treated equally or with equity at the same time but fairness should be such that treatment should be based on ethical and objective criteria among workers such that benefits are distributed similarly among similar individuals and differently to different individuals [59]. Distributive justice must always be that when employees compare their inputs to their outcomes and against those of co-workers for the same work category and in similar jobs in a different organization, very few disparities occur [39]. The implication for management is that fairness in the allocation of pay/salaries, rewards such as promotion and responsibilities, and workload should be done fairly. Employees put a lot of premium on these factors at the workplace and if they perceive unfairness the result is counterproductive behaviors; lateness, absenteeism, withdrawal, and general turnover, which are very detrimental to their performance and the performance of the organization. Distributive justice should be practiced to influence the OCB of civil servants in Kenya.

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